

EVALUATION OF THE GEOMETRICAL INFLUENCE OF THE STITCHING YARN ON THE STIFFNESS AND STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS MADE BY TAILORED FIBER PLACEMENT USING FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) is a textile manufacturing technology for placing continuous reinforcement fibers (roving) in arbitrary directions. A single roving is fixated by a stitching yarn on a flat textile base material using a double locked stitch, which enables the production of curvilinear fiber patterns with high degrees of freedom. This technology was invented to fully exploit the highly anisotropic material characteristics of reinforcing fibers in lightweight constructions, e.g. by placing rovings along the direction of principal stress. However, due to the necessary additional stitching yarn for the TFP process a small in-plane and out-of-plane waviness of the reinforcement fibers occurs, which leads to reduced stiffness and strength properties of the resulting fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) material. For part design it is important to know the impact of these effects on the effective material properties of FRP made by TFP. In this work a parametrical 3D finite element (FE) model was developed to determine the geometrical impact of the stitching yarn on the local fiber orientation, the local fiber volume content as well as the stress and strain distribution in a single unidirectional layer of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). This model describes a representative volume element (RVE), which is composed of separate volumes for the resin infiltrated roving, the necessary base material, resin rich zones around the upper stitching yarn, and for the lower stitching yarn. Additionally, the fiber volume content of the resin infiltrated roving zones is varied depending on the location in the RVE. The amplitude and the wavelength of the stitch yarn induced waviness on the roving itself and the geometry of resin rich areas around the stitching yarn were determined at cross sectional views of manufactured specimens. With the generated model it has been shown that the fiber volume content and the strain in fiber direction varies significantly depending on the position within the RVE.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their comparatively high density related strength and stiffness properties continuous FRP especially CFRP are used for structural parts in a wide range of application in order to save weight, energy and resources without trade-offs on durability and performance. Nowadays CFRP parts with thermoset matrices are mostly manufactured based on dry fabrics (woven fabrics, non-crimp fabrics (NCF), braided fabrics) where the resin is infiltrated afterwards, or based on resin pre-impregnated tapes or fabrics (e.g. filament winding, automated fiber placement). Often CFRP laminates are designed and manufactured as stacked unidirectional layers with different angles of fiber orientation which leads to quasi-isotropic stiffness and strength properties. In certain application with few dominant load cases a conventional laminate stacking does not fully exploit the potential of the CFRP material. Furthermore, even small differences between load direction and fiber orientation cause a

significant reduction of the mechanical properties, as shown in Figure 1. In order to minimize structural mass and to improve mechanical part properties a curvilinear fiber layout can be preferable.

Figure 1: Relative strength and stiffness of a CFRP laminate with unidirectional fiber orientation depending on the angle of the applied load direction

Figure 2: Basic principle of the TFP process

One finds various methods in literature which describe the derivation of load adapted fiber paths to exploit the unidirectional properties of CFRP in structural parts [1]. For the production of curvilinear fiber patterns the Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) technology was developed at the Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden e. V. TFP is a textile preform manufacturing technique which allows a flexible orientation of arbitrary reinforcement rovings (e.g. carbon, glass, aramid). Adapting embroidery technology, a single continuous roving is placed along programmable curves in a two-dimensional (2D) plane and fixated by a stitching yarn on a flat textile base material using a double locked stitch in a zigzag stitch pattern. The TFP principle is illustrated in Figure 2. The continuous fiber roving is oriented according to the design path by rotating the roving pipe and moving the base material in perpendicular directions.

The displacement volume of the necessary stitching yarn in combination with the zigzag stitch pattern causes a slight waviness of the reinforcement fibers in-plane and out-of-plane. This results in a reduction of the mechanical stiffness and strength properties. Furthermore due to the added stitching yarn the fiber volume content is not homogeneous distributed and typically on average lower compared to perfectly aligned unidirectional prepreg material. Currently, a conservative reduction ratio of about 10 percent is used in the structural design process of TFP CFRP parts to take these effects into account [1], [3].

In recent years various papers were published which have dealt with the influence of a stitching yarn in fabrics on the resulting laminate properties. In general the stitching yarn induces misalignment and waviness of the reinforcement fibers in-plane and out-of-plane, resin rich zones around the stitch zone, and local damage due to fiber fracture [5], [6].

Some approaches which takes the manufacturing process induced waviness of the rovings in to account are published for NCF composites using mesoscale finite element models [7], [8], [9]. NCF are made of layers from straight fiber tows held in position by a stitching yarn. While the stitch pattern is similar to the usual pattern for the TFP process, the rovings are placed with a discrete distance next to each other. This distance causes the main waviness and thus the additional induced waviness due to the stitching yarn is neglected in the approaches. Drapier and Wisnom developed a 2D FE model of a simple biaxial $0^\circ / 90^\circ$ NCF [7], [8]. The generalized plane-strain theory is used to represent the three-dimensional medium with an extruded 2D finite element model. It partially includes the roving waviness and the resin pockets due to the distance between the rovings. However, as mentioned above, the influence of the stitching yarn on the geometry is neglected. The rovings are represented in the 0° direction by a homogeneous band across the width and rovings along the 90° direction are represented by an ellipse of equivalent cross-sectional area. In References [7], [8] the waviness is defined by wavelength and amplitude with a sinusoidal shape. Ferreira et al. [9] investigated a 3D finite element

model based on two different approaches. In one approach the fiber waviness is modelled geometrically while in the other approach the fiber waviness is generated by a piece-wise linear material description. In both cases the course of the sewing yarn has been neglected. Stiffness properties and stresses/strains are studied with the model and compared to a classical approach. As a result a satisfactory agreement between both approaches in terms of the stiffness properties has been found.

In case of NCF material it is sufficient to leave out the course of the sewing yarn, due to fact that the gaps between the rovings mainly cause the fiber waviness and the resin pockets. In FRP materials made by TFP rovings are placed regularly gapless or partly overlapping. Furthermore the stitching yarn of one placed roving regularly penetrates the neighbor roving. Thus for proper modelling of TFP structures a detailed model which contains the course of the rovings and the stitching yarn is necessary.

Leipprand *et al.* [4] investigated the influence of stitching on the fiber misalignment in unidirectional CFRP sheets produced by TFP. On manufactured specimens the real fiber path was optically measured and statistically analyzed by means of Fourier analysis. With this method the amplitude and the wavelength of the rovings was derived. Additionally the influence of the TFP induced waviness on the strain behavior was determined in tensile tests using optical 3D strain analysis. Leipprand determined the influence of the TFP process parameters (see left detail of Figure 3) stitch distance SD (distance between two stitches parallel to the placing direction), stitch width SW (distance between two stitches orthogonal to the placing direction) and roving distance (RD) on the in-plane fiber waviness in a limited range. Based on experimental data a simplified numerical 3D model was developed, where the volume is rectangular and the waviness of the fiber orientation is formed by an in-plane sinusoidal orientation of the element coordinate system x-axis.

Figure 3: Snapshots of the TFP process (1 - 7) showing the placement of a third roving row and the sewing with a zigzag stitch pattern while the roving pipe moves from right to left. Details (left and top) with TFP process parameters and resulting fiber waviness due to stitching.

However, besides the in-plane fiber waviness other characteristics like the out-of-plane fiber waviness and the inhomogeneous material distribution with resin rich zones around the stitching yarn

and the resin infiltrated roving also influences the mechanical performance especially in respect to strength analysis.

Thus the aim of this work is the determination of the geometrical impact of the stitching yarn on the fiber waviness, the local fiber volume content as well as the stress and strain distribution in a single unidirectional CFRP layer made by TFP.

2 GEOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE TFP STRUCTURE

For a detailed meso-mechanical FE model it is necessary to analyze the geometrical characteristics of the structure. Several TFP manufacturing parameters have an impact on the resulting preform and basically two mechanisms influence the fiber waviness. First, the roving waviness due to the zigzag stitch pattern and second, the waviness due to the displacement volume of the stitching yarn (see e.g. upper detail in Figure 3 and Figure 5). For a unidirectional layer a continuous roving is placed in a meandering shape, such that straight roving segments are placed successively side by side with a slight overlap. Here the roving distance RD between two adjacent rows and the placing order is characteristic. The placing order influences the final shape of the rovings according to the stitching pattern.

Figure 4: Illustration of a TFP sample (left), the outline of sections in three orthogonal orientations (mid), combined three-dimensional view of micro sections on a TFP specimen with symmetrical layup (right)

Figure 5: Samples of micro sections in three orthogonal orientations. The different layers of the symmetrical structure are visible. The dimensions of resin rich zones and the out-of-plane fiber waviness can be measured.

Figure 3 shows the effect of fixation with a zigzag stitch pattern: during the fixation of a roving row on the base material the needle (which directs the stitching yarn) penetrates either the previously

placed roving row and the subjacent base material or just the base material. Thus gaps within the roving and holes in the base material are alternating. The following roving row, which is placed next to the previous row, will be partly on top of the stitching and the roving of the previous row. In Reference [4] the average in-plane waviness of the reinforcement fibers was determined. The wave amplitude for a stitch width of 5 mm was measured with 0.037 mm. As a basis for a detailed FE model a microscopic analysis was carried out. A unidirectional preform made by TFP with a SW of 5 mm, a SD of 3 mm and a RD of 2.2 mm was infiltrated with epoxy resin using resin transfer molding (RTM) technology in a cavity with constant thickness.

Layer	Mean thickness t [mm]	Standard deviation [mm]	Standard error [mm]
CFRP layer	0.369	± 0.0289	± 0.00498
Base material	0.159	± 0.0196	± 0.0031
Base material + EP layer	0.464	± 0.0336	± 0.0070
Total	1.185	± 0.0248	± 0.0055

Table 1: Layer thickness measured in micro sections (Figure 5)

Notation	Measuring point	Mean [mm]
Cross-section	▫ Gap between rovings	0.46
	▫ Width of a roving	2.19
Longitudinal section	▫ Amplitude of out-of-plane waviness A_{SYz}	max 0.10
	▫ Width of resin rich zone around stitch yarn p_{SY}	1.83
	▫ Width of the stitching yarn r_{SY}	0.25
Surface section	▫ Amplitude resin rich zone A_{SYy}	0.11
	▫ Width of resin rich zone	2.79

Table 2: Measurement results in the three kinds of micro sections (Figure 5)

The manufactured plates were cut to prepare micro sections in three orthogonal orientations (visualization in Figure 4) to determine the layer thickness, the dimensions of resin rich zones and the out-of-plane waviness (see results in Table 1 and Table 2). Some examples of micro sections are composed in Figure 5. The CFK roving, the base material as well as resin rich zones and the stitching yarn are visible. The out-of-plane waviness of the roving and the local variation of the fiber volume content due to the presence of the stitching yarn are shown in Detail B.

Material	Name of parameter	Physical quantity	Value	Unit
Fiber (f)	Longitudinal modulus	$E_{f\parallel}$	238000	MPa
	Transverse modulus	$E_{f\perp}$	16000	MPa
Epoxy (m)	Young's modulus	E_m	3150	MPa
	Shear modulus	G_m	1150	MPa
	Poisson's ratio	ν_m	0.37	
Base material (b)	Young's modulus	E_b	6035	MPa
	Shear modulus	G_b	2203	MPa
	Poisson's ratio	ν_b	0.37	
Composite (c)	Longitudinal modulus	$E_{c\parallel}$	83662.72	MPa
	Transverse modulus	$E_{c\perp}$	7737.15	MPa

Table 3: Mechanical properties of all material components and the derived stiffness values of a non-undulated unidirectional composite (CFRP) plate at the measured fiber volume content.

The amount of compaction pressure during the infiltrating process influences how much the stitching yarn is pushed into the CFRP layer. Other infiltration methods e.g. vacuum resin infusion [12] may lead to different results. Based on the measured thickness value the specimen consists of

16 % base material (filter paper in this case), 34 % carbon fiber and 50 % epoxy resin. The resin infiltrated roving zones approximately consists of 56 % carbon fiber. The determined data represent a sufficient basis for modelling. For comparison with the numerical results idealized stiffness values were calculated based on the measured results as a reference. Here ideally means a laminate containing the same stacking sequence and the same fiber volume content of perfectly straight fibers without resin rich zones. With the help of a micromechanical model and the rule of mixture the modulus of elasticity parallel to the fiber direction $E_{c||}$ and transverse to the fiber direction $E_{c\perp}$ was calculated [13]. The results are shown in Table 3.

3 NUMERICAL MODEL

The results of the geometrical analysis and the study of the roving course from Reference [4] were used to create a parametric finite element model of a representative volume element (RVE) which is repeatable in-plane to generate a complete laminate layer made by TFP. The modelling was done using the ANSYS Parametric Design Language (APDL) of the commercially available finite element software ANSYS. Due to the repeatability of the RVE it is sufficient to model a single wavelength section to define the material behavior. The RVE consist of separate zones for the resin infiltrated roving, the base material, and resin rich areas around the upper and lower stitching yarn. The in-plane waviness and the out-of-plane waviness of the roving reinforcement fibers are included in the RVE. Because of an almost equivalent tensile modulus of resin material and stitching yarn, they are combined and modelled as one volume in the RVE. In Figure 6 a half model of the RVE is shown embedded in the textile preform, while in Figure 7 three RVEs with different visible layers are represented.

Figure 6: Half model of the representative volume element embedded in the textile preform during the stitching process

Figure 7: Three rows of RVEs whereas different layers are visible. All layers are shown in the half model (bottom left). The stitching yarn is shown only in this illustration but is considered as resin material in the simulation.

The outer dimensions of the RVE are based on process parameters and measured data from Reference [3]. In x-direction the length of the RVE is equal to the SW, in y-direction the width of the RVE is the RD and in z-direction the laminate thickness is the height of the RVE. Superimposed to the cuboid, a cosine wave in the x-y-plane with the amplitude of the roving A_R , determined in Reference [3], is included to describe the outer volume of the RVE.

The origin of the Cartesian coordinate system of the RVE is in the lower left corner. All further geometry data is based on this coordinate system. Analogous to the micro sections a layer with a constant thickness which represents the lower stitching yarn surrounded by resin is modelled. A second layer was modelled on top of it, containing the resin infiltrated paper base material also with a constant thickness obtained by measurement on the micro sections. To achieve a homogeneous

laminate without gaps the SD has to be greater than the RD. Thus a roving partially overlaps the adjacent roving which was placed before as well as the applied stitching yarn.

Figure 8: Illustration of the relevant parameter of the RVE in two levels - on top of the base material and on top of the RVE

As shown in Figure 7 due to the overlap the RVE contains volume parts from two adjacent rovings - the subjacent volume of the resin infiltrated roving specified as “Roving 1” and the adjacent and partially overlaying resin infiltrated roving specified as “Roving 0”. In total both volumes represent the volume of one resin infiltrated roving. The course of both rovings in the x-y-plane is identical and corresponds to the cosine wave of the outer volume. The residual volume is formed by the upper stitching yarn surrounded by resin pockets. The displacement volume of the stitching yarn compresses both rovings locally, according to the course of the stitching yarn. The RVE includes parts of three upper stitching yarns, which in total represent the volume of one upper stitching yarn (see Figure 7 and Figure 8). The course of the stitching yarn in z-direction reflects the course of roving 1 and roving 0 at their adjacent boundary surfaces. According to the course of the stitching yarn the dimension of the resulting resin pockets in x-, y- and z-direction were obtained from the micro sections. In the model a sinusoidal shape was chosen to describe the shape of the resin pocket. With the used approach all roving volumes including the “dents” due to the stitching yarn can be described mathematically.

Figure 9: Resin areas of the RVE: a) resin zones around stitching yarn and additional layers in a view, where some zones were cut out for visibility b) front view and c) rear view of the half RVE including the meshing - zones of resin material are marked in red, zones of roving material are marked in bright grey.

It has to be mentioned that in order to achieve a suitable mesh, a very thin layer with resin properties is modelled in non-stitching yarn affected zones between both, adjacent rovings and between a roving and the borders of the RVE to avoid ill-shaped elements. This leads to an approximately 1.8 % higher fiber volume content in the roving volumes, which in turn leads to slightly higher stress levels in these zones under loading. These volumes are shown in Figure 9 together with

the afore mentioned resin pockets colored in red. The minimal SW of a TFP device is 1 mm which is always higher than half the wavelength of the resin pocket caused by the stitching yarn. The maximum RD depends on the roving material. With the 12 K carbon fiber material (800 TEX), which was chosen for this study, in our lab the maximum RD is about 2.2 mm to achieve a fully covered laminate with an almost even thickness distribution. At the measured fiber volume content of 56 % this RD results in a laminate thickness of 0.35 mm which represents the minimum layer thickness producible by TFP with this setup. The hold down device on the embroidery head limits the maximum thickness of the preform to 5.0 mm and thus in theory the minimum RD is 0.12 mm. Due to the placement behavior of a roving in practice the RD should not be lower than 0.75 mm. When applying lower RDs the second roving tends to slide down on the slope of the first roving and so forth. Thus the placement accuracy cannot be guaranteed anymore. Furthermore for the applicability of the laminate theory the thickness of a layer should be as thin as possible.

As mentioned earlier and seen in the micro sections of Figure 5, the fiber volume content (FVC) varies in different zones of the specimen. To take this into account a variable fiber volume content was implemented in the model. Small pieces of volumes, which form the CFRP layer, were compared to a model with resin rich zones and without. This information in combination with the global fiber volume content (calculated in dependence of the model dimensions, which are gained from the micro sections) allows the calculation of the local FVC. The distribution of the FVC for a SW of 5 mm and a SD of 3 mm is shown in Figure 10. According to the micro sections, areas with a higher concentration of fibers are located next to the stitching yarn. As shown in Figure 10 despite a global fiber volume content of 56 % locally the fiber volume content in the model reaches values up to 81 %. Taking in to account the artificially added resin material at model boundaries, the realistic fiber volume content in these roving zones still reaches approximately 79 %. Therefore the probability of directly contacted carbon fibers without a resin layer in between is high. This can lead to an earlier crack initiation and thus to a significantly reduced off-axis strength and off-axis fractural strain compared to unidirectional non stitched laminates.

Figure 10: Distribution of the local fiber volume content within the RVE

Figure 11: Boundary conditions (top) and Finite element with nodes (I-P) and element coordinate system (ECOS) (bottom)

The boundary conditions are shown in Figure 11. One side of the RVE was constrained as a fixed end, such that a lateral contraction is possible (fixed in x-direction and in the middle of the cross section in y-direction). Due to the fact that symmetrical laminates are used for structural parts symmetrical boundary conditions in z-direction were applied as well. The opposite side was loaded with a tensile force of 500 N.

In this study an 8-node structural solid element with the option of orthotropic material properties (SOLID185) was chosen. Due to a detailed volume description a regular mesh is ensured and the further alignment of element coordinate systems (ECOS) is possible. These ECOS form the basis for the orthotropic material orientations. Here the element edges of each element are used to form average vectors (v_n respectively v_m). After that the generated vectors are used to orientate the element coordinate system, whereas the x-axis is orientated in fiber direction (see Figure 11).

4 RESULTS

For the given stitching and material parameters the numerical results for the tensile modulus were compared to analytically calculated stiffness data parallel to the fiber direction, based on an equal FVC and material properties as shown in Table 3. The results are shown in Figure 12. With the TFP parameters for this study the reduction is about 2 % compared to perfectly unidirectional aligned fibers. It has to be mentioned that due to the chosen base material the absolute stiffness value of the TFP laminate is lower compared to plain UD CFRP laminates. The paper base material with its low stiffness was chosen to minimize the impact of the base material on the orthotropic behavior of a UD laminate. In real structural parts carbon fiber fabrics or carbon fiber fleece materials are used as base material which does not significantly lower the global laminate properties.

Figure 12: Tensile modulus - comparison of the numerical results and the theoretical stiffness of a perfectly unidirectional aligned laminate with identical material parameters

Figure 13: Local strain distribution in fiber direction of the CFRP layer (resin and base material sections are not shown)

In Figure 13 the local strain distribution is shown. The maximum strain value in fiber direction of about 0.58 % is located at the corner of the model where the fiber volume content reaches the highest values within the model. Other local maxima are located around resin rich zones next to the position of the stitching yarn. Compared to the average strain of a unidirectional laminate without fiber waviness (0.46 %) the local strain within the RVE (0.58 %) is about 26 % higher. Sufficient numerical convergence is found if the element size is lower than 2 % of the volume of the RVE. Due to the inhomogeneous fiber volume content the stiffness parallel to the fiber direction varies in the same way as the fiber volume content does. Subsequently according to the rule of mixture in a zone with a higher FVC the stiffness is higher as well (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Tensile modulus distribution of the CFRP layer within the model at the given TFP parameters and measured global fiber volume content of the specimen

Figure 15: Stress in fiber direction under uniaxial loading in relation to fiber volume content

To evaluate the stress in fiber direction the local fiber volume content has to be taken in to account. In Figure 15 the pure fiber parallel stress is plotted. Due to geometric effects, the resin pockets and the stitching yarn behave like a filled hole. Maximal stress levels are located next to the stitching yarn course. At the given load locally the maximum stress in fiber direction is about 1332 N/mm². In the perfectly aligned reference laminate the stress distribution is uniform and at the given load the stress in fiber direction is 1100 N/mm². Thus locally the fiber parallel stress in the TFP laminate is up to 21 % higher which subsequently leads to a lower fractural strength compared to the reference laminate.

It has to be mentioned that the determined results are only valid for the chosen TFP parameter set. If other values for the SW or SD are applied other local values for stress and strain are obtained.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper presents a numerical study on the influence of a stitching yarn on the resulting mechanical properties of continuous carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) made by Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) using a typical TFP parameter set. Starting with a geometrical analysis using micro sections of manufactured specimens, a detailed view of the internal structure was obtained.

The micro sections were used to measure the dimensions of the roving, the stitching yarn, resin rich zones and amplitudes of fiber waviness. Based on these data and previously obtained waviness data a FE model of a repeatable representative volume element (RVE) was developed. The RVE reflects the inhomogeneous local fiber volume content due to the displacement volume of the stitching yarn and the waviness of the roving. The geometric influence of the stitching yarn reduces the mechanical performance of unidirectional CFRP laminates manufactured by TFP compared to perfectly aligned unidirectional CFRP laminates with an identical global fiber volume content and without waviness.

With the given TFP parameter set the global stiffness parallel to the fiber direction is 2 % lower compared to the perfectly aligned unidirectional CFRP laminate. Locally the differences are much more pronounced. In the numerical model in zones close to the stitching yarn up to 26 % higher strain values parallel to the fiber direction were determined. Thus lower global tensile strength values are expected. A variation of TFP process parameters changes the average wave amplitude of the fibers and the amount of stitching yarn in the RVE which leads to significant differences in the resulting material properties. In contrast to the relatively strong geometrical impact of the stitching yarn on the local stress levels it has to be emphasized that due to the high flexibility of the technology, fibers can follow directly calculated load paths and according to Figure 1 and as investigated in Reference [1], the final mechanical performance of structural parts can be much higher compared to CFRP parts made of stacked UD prepreg layers.

In further investigations the numerical results will be compared to experimentally obtained data, regarding a global and local stiffness distribution. The qualitative behavior of different stitching parameters on the stiffness results is similar. However, for quantitative numerical data on specific production parameter sets further specimen have to be produced to obtain relevant dimensions from micro sections.

Thus, the RVE approach of this work provides the basis for calculating effective material data for FRP manufactured by TFP which can be applied for macro scaled FE modelling specifically tailored to the corresponding production parameters.

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